

Deliverable D6.4

Pilot (DE) Technical report and achieved results (1|2)

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

Table of contents

Deliverable report	2
Document Contributors	2
Document History	2
Disclaimer	3
Table of contents	4
List of Abbreviations	5
1 Pilot overview	6
2 Implementation of technologies	8
2.1 Development and Installation of the Data Logger (T3.4.1)	8
2.2 Development and Configuration of Software (T3.4.1)	11
2.3 Interfaces to Fuel Station and Belt Scale System (T3.4.1)	13
2.4 Development of the Geofence-System (T3.4.2)	17
2.5 Platform design implementation (Task 4.2)	18
2.6 AI algorithms (Task 4.3)	19
2.7 BIM (Task 4.4)	20
3 Results	21
3.1 Data Logger and Raw Data Transmission	21
3.2 Development of the KPIs	21
3.3 Material Tracking using the Geofences System	23
4 Impact assessment	24
5 Future	25
6 Conclusions	26
List of Figures	27
List of Tables	28

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
3D	three-dimensional
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
D (number)	Deliverable (number of deliverable)
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
GA	Grant Agreement
GPS	Global Positioning System
H&S	Health and Safety
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying system
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KTA	Key Technology Area
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
WP	Work Package
Unit	Description
km/ m / mm	kilometre / meter / millimetre
l	Litre
rpm	revolutions per minute
t /kg /g /µg	ton / kilogram / gram /microgram
a / h / min / s or (sec)	year / hour / minute / second

1 Pilot overview

The quarry Mammendorf run by CSI is located around 20 km west of Magdeburg in Germany. The hard rock quarry produces high quality andesite products that are used in several applications in the asphalt, concrete and construction industry.

At the beginning of the production process the blasted rock is hauled to the pre-crusher with dump trucks. The crushed rock is stored on a large buffer stockpile. During the following process the material is crushed and screened multiple times to produce the high-quality aggregate fractions needed. The treatment plant and parts of the quarry are shown in Figure 1.

In detail the quarry side consists of the following main areas:

- Mining areas with four to five benches.
- Overburden and topsoil removal on the upper benches.
- Dump side for overburden and waste material.
- Pre-crusher and buffer stockpile.
- The treatment plant for secondary and tertiary crushing, screening and direct loading.
- Multiple stockpile areas for separated storage of the finished fractions (products).
- Infrastructure area with offices, workshop, truck scale, fuel station and parking location.

An overview of the whole pilot quarry with a description of the main areas is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Drone image of the treatment plant in the quarry Mammendorf.

Figure 2. Overview of the whole quarry Mammendorf with short site description.

The main DEQ subject targeted in the pilot Mammendorf is the management, data recording and process evaluation of the mobile fleet used for mining, overburden removal, dumping and product loading. The quarry is the reference pilot for mobile machinery and its more efficient use and reduction of emissions.

The main KPIs for the pilot Mammendorf are the minimisation of transport distances, the reduction of fuel-consumption, CO₂ emissions, as well as downtime and repairs.

The Mammendorf pilot site is thereby connected to the following activities defined in the GA:

- Mobile equipment digitalisation using special HW.
- Mobile data collection, transmission and process evaluation using developed SW solutions.
- Novel geofence system for material tracking.
- Near-real time process modelling.
- Data integration in the BIM and IQS.

- Development of artificial intelligence algorithms.
- Environmental simulations platform.
- Social acceptance and communication with policy makers.

The main work of the CSI-team is in WP6 T6.4 (pilot implementation at CSI's quarry) but relates to WP3 T3.4 including the installations of data loggers in the mixed OEM mobile quarry equipment (wheel loaders, dump and road trucks and excavators), the installation of an RTK-system, and the set-up of a geofence system for material tracking. The data from the data logger will be used to evaluate central KPIs from the mobile fleet including for example fuel consumption, working and idling times and technical alerts. The KPIs will be displayed in the DH&P expert system that functions as fleet management system. Based on that the general processes are validated, further KPIs are analysed and process optimization KPIs will be conducted from the quarry staff. The target is to minimise fuel consumption, improve equipment efficiency, minimise idle- and downtimes and improve the internal road conditions as well as H&S measures. All activities described are related to KTA 3.3.

The further activities for the general data integration on BIM, AI and IQS level are related to KTA 4.1, KTA 4.2 and KTA 4.3. The environmental simulation platform to be set up for Mammendorf is developed following KTA 6.1. The Social and communication targets are developed in KSA 7.1 and KSA 8.1.

2 Implementation of technologies

2.1 Development and Installation of the Data Logger (T3.4.1)

The specifications for the universal data logger have been defined between CSI, DH&P and the hardware manufacturer in order to fulfil the needs of the demanding and harsh quarry environment. The logger must be compatible with different OEM CAN-BUS Systems and interfaces. The data transmission must be reliable and internal storage capacity must be sufficient to bridge times of reduced network availability. For data transmission different options including the option of an on-side buffer server have been evaluated. WLAN, Bluetooth and Mobile Communication (GSM) must be covered from the data logger to allow a broad spectrum of data transmission and sensor connection technologies. The logger must be equipped with internal power supply to be able to record positions or transmit data even if the machine is turned off. As the position of the mobile machines is essential for almost every target KPI, the GPS module of the logger must have the ability to be optionally equipped with RTK capabilities including the connection to an external reference station. The logger must be dust and water protected and show a high durability from heat, cold and vibrations. The different functions of the data logger are explained in the deliverable D3.8 of WP3. The logger was tested in a different CSI quarry for 3 weeks in order to fulfil the defined requirements and pre-test possible installation positions and issues.

The Mammendorf quarry fleet consists of the following machines to be equipped with the data logger in the DEQ project when M3.3 (final installation and IQS integration) is completed in M36. As indicated the first mobile machines were already equipped in the first installation phase before M3.1 (Mobile Machinery sensors ready for 1st implementation campaign in the pilots (prototypes)) in M25. The other machines will be equipped in the second installation phase.

Dump Trucks / Road Trucks

- Used for material hauling of blasted rock, overburden, fines and products.
- 4 Caterpillar 775G dump trucks built between 2015 – 2022 (1 dump truck equipped in the 1st installation stage).
- 1 Komatsu HD325 dump truck built 2022.
- 2 Volvo FMX 500 four-axel trucks built 2022 (1 truck equipped in the 1st installation stage).

Excavators

- Used for loading of blasted rock or overburden materials.
- 2 Caterpillar 374 NG/FL built 2020 and 2022 (1 excavator equipped in the 1st installation stage).

- 1 Caterpillar 352F XE built 2017.
- 1 Caterpillar 329 FL built 2015.

Wheel-Loaders

- Used for loading of products to customers, fines and auxiliary work.
- 3 Caterpillar 972 M XE built between 2015 and 2021.
- 1 Komatsu WA 475 built 2020 (equipped in the 1st installation stage).

The installation in the first stage has been completed. Several problems came up with the CAN Bus connection when installing the data logger that were solved with technicians on site or in contact to the OEMs. The installation positions on the four machines of the stage 1 installation are given in the following figures:

Figure 3 Dump Truck (Caterpillar 775G) with installed data logger.

Figure 4 Truck (Volvo FMX 500) with installed data logger.

Figure 5 Excavator (Caterpillar 374) with installed data logger.

Figure 6 Wheel Loader (Komatsu WA 475) with installed data logger.

Due to the sufficient mobile network connection in the quarry the on-side buffer server has not been needed for now. The data from the installed data loggers is transferred via a mobile network connection directly to the buffer server of the hardware manufacturer. From there the data is transferred via an API directly to the DH&P AutoPLAN expert system.

2.2 Development and Configuration of Software (T3.4.1)

The AutoPLAN expert system is structured in the user frontend including visual mapping and dashboard functions and the raw data background handling where the incoming data from the mobile machines is managed. The incoming raw data is hereby parameterized and stored in a SQL database.

After accessing the DH&P AutoPLAN expert system the user can access the following main functions. There are many functions of the AutoPLAN expert system that will not be used or further developed in the DEQ project. Those functions are neglected and not further described in this deliverable.

- Mapping tool for visualisation of any geodata including digital orthophotos and topographical information.
- Machine activity and track visualisation including visualisation of the defined 3D-geofences, vehicle speed and altitude profiles.
- Display of all raw data sets recorded for each mobile machine including comparison of data sets and graph visualisation to manually analyse errors; check function to see available data sets stored for each machine and to quickly identify missing data (data gaps).
- Dashboards for the plant and each machine to be used by the quarry staff to show defined KPIs calculated from the machine and additional plant data for verification.

From the raw data the defined KPIs regarding fuel consumption, mass movement, drive tracks and material tracking are calculated. The KPIs can be accessed and evaluated using the single KPI overview shown in Figure 9.

The KPIs will be presented to the plant staff in dashboards, which are currently under development. The aim is to give a fast and structured overview of the overall fleet performance and the relevant indicators across machines from different manufactures/brands.

Figure 9. Single KPI overview and calculation (here fuel consumption)

2.3 Interfaces to Fuel Station and Belt Scale System (T3.4.1)

For validation of the recorded mobile data, interfaces to the existing technology for automated data recording are established to be integrated in the expert system. This includes the integration of the main belt-scales installed right after the pre-crusher and the refuelling and documentation software that integrates data from the fixed fuel station and the mobile fuel truck equipped with the same system. For both data sources APIs or/and manual input functions are integrated into the expert system. Once running the data will be used to automatically validate and supplement the data gathered from the mobile machines.

The belt scales 1.21 and 1.23 to be integrated are installed behind the pre-crusher and at the belt for the separated fines. The accumulated values of both scales give the total daily gross production transported to and dumped into the pre-crusher. Both belt scales are of a similar type/build. The API will exchange the accumulated daily production in tons and a current load factor in tons per hour. The installed belt scale 1.21 just after the pre crusher is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Installation position of the belt scale 1.21 behind the pre-crusher.

The fuel used for all mobile machines is either tanked from the fixed fuel station next to the plant or from the mobile fuel truck. All employees running mobile machinery at the quarry have a vehicle specific fuel chip that has to be used for each refuelling process. Before the refuelling process can be started the chips need to be placed on the chip reader at both fuel stations and the odometer (km) or the current engine hours (h) need to be entered. For each machine in the quarry the total amount of fuel tanked for each refilling process as well as accumulated values and the engine hours or the driven kilometres are exchanged for validation via the developed API with the expert system. The expert system automatically validates the KPIs calculated from the recorded mobile data with the data exchanged from the belt scales and the fuel management software.

The fixed fuel station and the mobile fuel truck as well as the installed chip readers are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Fixed fuel station (left) and mobile fuel station (upper right) and chip reader (lower right).

2.4 Integration of external Sensors on the machines

Some of the mobile machinery is additionally equipped with non-OEM external sensors. In Case of CSI all wheeled machines are equipped with tire-pressure-monitoring systems (TPMS) (see Figure 12). These consist of sensors on each wheel, measuring the pressure and the temperature inside the tire and sending it via radio-signal to a control-unit inside the cabin. All data is displayed on that unit. The progress of temperature and pressure is stored in an internal storage. In case of low- or high-pressure or overtemperature, the system is creating an alert. As tire-pressure is a very important factor to operate a machine in a safe and efficient way, it is mandatory to connect the TPMS-systems to the data-logger and transfer the data to the platform.

Figure 12 The Sensor and Display of the installed tire-pressure-monitoring-system.

Some of the wheel loaders at CSI are equipped with non-OEM-weight-scales. The reason is that most OEM-weighbridges are not calibratable legal for trade. The non-OEM-weight-scales monitor and store all material-movements of the machine. For the mass-flow-recording and to determine and optimize the efficiency of the machine, this data is mandatory. The weight-information must be connected to the GPS-data and the geofencing, to be part of the mass-flow-capturing. The display of the external weighting system on a wheel loader is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 The external weight scale on a wheel loader.

2.5 Development of the Geofence-System (T3.4.2)

The first 3D-Geofence prototype had to be updated with a current topographical model to show the current quarry outlay, which is quickly changing due to the high production rates of the quarry. A high-quality drone flight and the photogrammetric visualisation of the quarry in a 3D point cloud was conducted during the DEQ project (see Figure 14).

Figure 14 Screenshot from the high-resolution point cloud used for developing the topographical model.

Using the 3D surveying data, a detailed topographical model has been prepared for the quarry shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Topographical Model of the quarry Mammendorf integrated in the AutoPLAN expert system.

Based on the topographical models and all areas source or target for material transport a temporary basic 3D-geofence structure has been established for material tracking and activity detection (see Figure 16). This model is to be refined in the further course of the project – especially regarding a further differentiation between overburden removal and rock extraction as well as stockpile differentiation.

Figure 16 Temporary Geofence structure for the quarry Mammendorf

2.6 Platform design implementation (Task 4.2)

The data lake for the pilot Mammendorf has been set up in WP4. In the future all data recorded from the mobile machines will be stored in the data lake and then used by different DEQ systems, authorised by CSI, to use the recorded data for further KPI calculation. So far test data of the four machines has been exchanged with the data lake. The general data exchange will start once the API is fully developed by DH&P (WP3). The data format and API definition is supported by DH&P. The data has not been validated yet. This will for instance be done by comparing the gathered data with data from the OEM-data systems of the single machines, the data of the fuel-system and the actual situation in the quarry. Finally selected KPIs can be uploaded to the data lake to be used by other partners expert systems (i.e. environmental simulations by WP5). An example of the data lake for the pilot Mammendorf is shown in Figure 17.

Actions	ID	Quarry Process	Sub Process	Sharing Description	Sharing Item Description	Sharing Date
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	Environment and Energy (KTA6)	Environment and Energy	This file represents EPD-M1 and LCA_Results	test files for CSI	11/01/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	AI	forecast	Electricity prices in Portugal		10/07/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) (KTA3.3)	Loading and Hauling - DHP	These files represent the mobile machineries data of CSI	proxy-dhp-asset-values	21/08/2023

Items per page: 20 | 1 - 3 of 3 | < > >>

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Figure 17 List of files uploaded to the data lake from the quarry Mammendorf.

2.7 AI algorithms (Task 4.3)

Related to Task 4.3 Sigma develops a system for acoustic detection of anomalies in the production process of the fixed stationary plant. CSI will support SIGMA in developing that system by providing data. CSI and Sigma decided that the most useful place to install a detector in the first step, is the secondary-crusher Sandvik CH 660. A trouble-free operation of this machine is essential for the whole production process. Sigma develops, respectively tests sensors that are able to withstand the rough conditions of a quarry-plant with vibrations, dust, water and differing temperatures. The sensors will be installed to measure the sounds and the vibrations of the crusher. As soon as this is done the collected data will be uploaded to the data pool. AI will define a normal range of sounds and vibrations. Afterwards AI will be able to detect abnormalities and create warnings. In the future this system will potentially help to avoid technical errors, help to optimize the material-flow inside the crusher and be an indicator for predictive maintenance.

Figure 18 Inlay of a sensor for the measurement of abnormalities of a crusher.

2.8 BIM (Task 4.4)

The BIM is developed with APP. So far KPI definition with APP and data exchange needs to be finished in order to set up the model.

Figure 19 BIM Model.

3 Results

3.1 Data Logger and Raw Data Transmission and GPS connection

The data logger has successfully been installed and connected to the CAN-BUS system in four machines from three different OEMs. The logger proves to be reliable in the quarry environment and data transmission is reliable. The data logger is the base of the mobile data logging expert system developed and validated from DH&P and CSI in WP3 and WP6. The data transmission is built up and data is transmitted every few minutes to the AutoPLAN expert system for storage and normalisation. The data connection is reliable and can be applied for the other machines. The GPS connection in the quarry is sufficient in x and y-direction. The altitude data is only insufficient on the lower benches of the pit. A RTK installation will be tested to overcome those problems.

3.2 Development of the KPIs

The basis for calculating the KPIs (or data outputs) is the recorded raw data (or data inputs) of the equipped machines. This data is, with exception of the weighting information of the mobile machines, available for all four of the so far equipped machines. In accordance with the quarry needs and the KPIs defined in the GA the following target KPIs are defined (see Table 1). These KPIs are (if applicable for the machine) calculated for each machine individually. From the individual KPIs global KPIs for the whole fleet are calculated (i.e. total fuel usage of the fleet, total fuel usage for overburden removal etc). As the first project targets are the individual machine KPIs as the base for further calculations, the global plant KPIs are not listed in the following.

Table 1 Defined machine KPIs for the pilot Mammendorf

KPI	Description	Unit
Operational time	Total time the engine is running	h
Idle time	Time the engine is idling	h
Utilisation	Ratio of idling to operational time	%
Fuel usage total/average	Amount of fuel used in total and in average	l and l/h
Fuel usage per activity	Total and average fuel used for activities (i.e. overburden removal, several machines)	l/h
Cycles Completed	Times driven between a source and a target geofence (i.e. mining bench to pre-crusher and back)	n
Tonnages produced of different materials	Material transported with differentiation between blasted hard rock, overburden, waste and product	t
Tonnages average	Average production of a machine per working time	t/h
Engine hours	Current engine hours readings of the machine	h
Warnings	Current warnings of machine	-
Tire pressure/temperature	Current pressure and temperature of tires	Bar/ °C
Distance driven (+ loaded)	Total distance driven, Total distance driven loaded	km
Maximum and average Speed	The maximum and average speed driven by the machine	km/h
Material tracking	Full material tracking with visualisation	-

The basic KPIs (used for almost all further analysis) are currently calculated and will be validated in the next phase. This includes operational, idling and working times, distances and speeds and fuel consumption.

An example for the calculated fuel consumption (l/h) for one day the current results (to be further improved and validated) are as follows (no data for wheel loader WA475 in the selected time period):

Figure 20 Calculated Fuel use (l/h) for a given day.

In comparison to the actual average fuel usage (l/h) documented in the pilot (see Figure 21) the fuel data seems to be in a realistic range or a bit too low. The detailed use of the machine in the calculated time needs to be evaluated and the general calculation period needs to be longer to develop a comprehensible KPI.

Figure 21 Calculated fuel use (l/h) for a given day in relation to the actual average use documented by the pilot.

3.3 Material Tracking using the Geofences System

The temporary 3D-geofence structure has been developed based on a new detailed survey of the quarry and a derived topographical model. In the next step a prototype algorithm links the equipment position to the 3D-geofences (see example for the CAT dumper 775G in Figure 22. After error elimination due to wrong geofence allocation the number of cycles between two geofences will be counted automatically (i.e. mining bench to pre-crusher and back to mining bench). Linked to the information of the weighing systems of the mobile machines the material will be tracked and the mass flow can be visualised and analysed.

Components	Color	Geofence	Start	End	Start	End	Duration [s]	Z min.	Z max.	Distance [m]	Distance [m]	Average Speed [m/s]
Categories		Plant Site Road	1696227349	1696227758	07:15:49	07:22:38	409.0	5.420	122.800	365.2	945.9	2.3
Types		Plant Site Road	1696227761	1696227764	07:22:41	07:22:44	3.0	113.770	115.100	10.1	10.1	3.4
Components		Primary Crusher	1696227787	1696227785	07:22:47	07:23:05	18.0	114.730	123.940	55.9	56.6	3.1
Data		Primary Crusher	1696227788	1696227791	07:23:08	07:23:11	3.0	125.990	126.750	8.6	8.6	2.9
Tracks		Primary Crusher	1696227794	1696227839	07:23:14	07:23:59	45.0	128.170	135.950	12.7	36.2	0.8
Transfers		Primary Crusher	1696227842	1696227875	07:24:02	07:24:35	33.0	126.510	127.440	24.4	35.5	1.1
GPS Import		Plant Site Road	1696227878	1696227890	07:24:38	07:24:50	12.0	118.880	125.530	67.6	68.6	5.7
Geofence Update		Mining Bench 73	1696227893	1696227930	07:24:53	07:25:38	45.0	75.770	117.230	311.8	368.2	8.2
Availabilities		Mining Bench 73	1696227941	1696227941	07:25:41	07:25:41	0.0	74.490	74.490	0.0	0.0	0.0
Label		Mining Bench 60	1696228004	1696228124	07:26:44	07:28:44	120.0	53.040	60.960	14.8	39.2	0.3
Label Categories		Mining Bench 60	1696228127	1696228484	07:28:47	07:34:44	357.0	62.510	120.600	556.3	659.7	1.8
Label		Plant Site Road	1696228487	1696228505	07:34:47	07:35:05	18.0	121.000	127.500	70.5	71.9	4.0
Parameter		Plant Site Road	1696228508	1696228532	07:35:08	07:35:32	24.0	128.400	129.430	21.2	48.5	2.0
Categories		Primary Crusher	1696228535	1696228571	07:35:35	07:36:11	36.0	122.290	127.990	2.3	5.5	0.2
Parameter Definitions		Primary Crusher	1696228574	1696228667	07:36:14	07:37:47	93.0	117.370	121.650	2.2	12.5	0.1
Parameter		Primary Crusher	1696228670	1696228679	07:37:50	07:37:59	9.0	122.160	122.660	0.0	1.4	0.2
Values		Plant Site Road	1696228682	1696228715	07:38:02	07:38:35	33.0	119.130	121.150	23.6	30.9	0.9
Representations		Plant Site Road	1696228718	1696228730	07:38:38	07:38:50	12.0	113.990	119.980	66.0	66.5	5.5
Ranges		Mining Bench 60	1696228733	1696228835	07:38:53	07:40:35	102.0	61.390	113.330	548.1	645.7	6.3
Reports		Mining Bench 60	1696228838	1696228838	07:40:38	07:40:38	0.0	60.930	60.930	0.0	0.0	0.0
		Mining Bench 60	1696228841	1696228865	07:40:41	07:41:05	24.0	61.040	62.240	4.3	9.3	0.4
		Plant Site Road	1696228908	1696228929	07:51:48	07:52:09	21.0	115.480	125.370	74.0	75.1	3.6
		Primary Crusher	1696229532	1696229559	07:52:12	07:52:39	27.0	122.510	126.770	13.9	54.2	2.0
		Primary Crusher	1696229562	1696229580	07:52:42	07:53:00	18.0	121.020	121.900	1.1	1.1	0.1
		Plant Site Road	1696229603	1696229622	07:53:03	07:53:42	39.0	122.370	125.460	23.0	36.9	0.9
		Plant Site Road	1696229625	1696229640	07:53:45	07:54:00	15.0	114.380	124.210	81.9	83.6	5.6
		Mining Bench 60	1696229643	1696229724	07:54:03	07:55:24	81.0	62.220	111.770	537.2	586.4	7.2
		Mining Bench 60	1696229727	1696229748	07:55:27	07:55:48	21.0	59.440	60.730	6.3	7.8	0.4
		Mining Bench 60	1696229751	1696229754	07:55:51	07:55:54	3.0	61.530	62.010	6.5	6.5	2.2
		Mining Bench 60	1696229797	1696229814	07:55:57	07:56:54	57.0	56.600	60.860	3.0	27.3	0.5
		Mining Bench 60	1696229817	1696229841	07:56:57	07:57:21	24.0	61.190	62.970	1.3	1.8	0.1
		Mining Bench 60	1696229844	1696229867	07:57:24	07:58:27	123.0	55.810	60.630	0.7	7.0	0.1
		Mining Bench 60	1696229870	1696230123	07:59:30	08:02:03	153.0	61.030	64.970	57.2	80.1	0.5
		Mining Bench 60	1696230126	1696230126	08:02:06	08:02:06	0.0	60.850	60.850	0.0	0.0	0.0
		Plant Site Road	1696230129	1696230270	08:02:09	08:04:30	141.0	61.270	114.200	504.7	567.3	4.0
		Plant Site Road	1696230273	1696230294	08:04:33	08:04:54	21.0	117.440	126.320	73.7	74.7	3.6
		Primary Crusher	1696230297	1696230363	08:04:57	08:06:03	66.0	124.860	127.800	18.3	56.2	0.9

Figure 22 Connection between the vehicle position and the 3D-geofences.

4 Impact assessment

The mobile quarry fleet is besides the treatment plant the major energy consumer in the pilot and furthermore related to very high investments costs due to high usage and wear of the employed machinery. An optimal machine utilization and the adequate operation is vital for a reliable and efficient production of the quarry. Due to the high importance of the mobile fleet general indicators, respectively aggregated data about the performance of the mobile machines are already available. But the documentation requires either manual and therefore additional work that is prone to errors or is only available in a low granularity. The integration of different data sources, i.e. the existing OEM-specific systems in a single expert system, which is needed for effective control of the whole mobile fleet does not exist so far.

The impact that the DEQ project has and will have on the pilot site Mammendorf is as follows: As soon as the all data of the installed logger, the external sensors, the fuel-station and the weight-bridges are transferred to the software on a reliable base, and the KPIs are validated, the CSI-Team can work with the AutoPLAN expert system. The transport-process of the material from the pit to the primary-crusher and all other movements of the equipment will be fully monitored. The tool can then be used to optimize all loading-, transport-, and other processes realized with the mobile equipment. The roadways inside the quarries and their maintenance cycles can be optimized. Abnormalities and problems in the processes can be detected and corrected fast. Technical problems or operating errors of the machines can be detected in a fast and reliable way.

So far, the equipment of the data logger on four machines has shown reliable data recording and transmission but some data gaps (especially data from mobile weighting systems and external sensors) are present and identified. The data has been used to calculate first basic indicators that are validated with the already available data provided manually. The further equipment of the whole machinery fleet is prepared and the data visualisation and integration are enhanced. Due to the early KPI status, the fleet only partially equipped and the data gaps the DEQ installation has not clearly impacted the decision making in the quarry and the DEQ operational improvements can therefore not validated yet.

5 Future

- 1) The future development includes the installation of the remaining maximum 11 data loggers on the following machines. The number may vary slightly in order of the further development of the project. The total number of equipped data loggers will be around 15. Machines to be equipped additionally to the four already equipped machines:
 - 3 Caterpillar 775G dump trucks.
 - 1 Komatsu HD325 dump truck.
 - 1 Volvo FMX 500 four-axle truck.
 - 1 Caterpillar 374.
 - 1 Caterpillar 352F XE.
 - 1 Caterpillar 329 FL.
 - 3 Caterpillar 972 M XE.
- 2) The test of the RTK hardware to improve the positioning of the machines - especially concerning the recorded altitude and the 3D-geofence allocation.
- 3) The implementation of the installed mobile weighting systems when possible or the development of alternative source of the transported tonnages.
- 4) The full implementation of the fuel tanking data (fuel station + mobile tank) and existing belt scale data for validation.
- 5) The integration of the tire pressure sensors.
- 6) The refinement and validation of the KPIs calculated from the recorded raw data.
- 7) The set-up of an optimized dashboard structure to present all calculated KPIS in a structured manner.
- 8) Final validation and definition of optimization potential under consideration of the defined pilot targets of the GA.

6 Conclusions

The DEQ development in the pilot Mammendorf is steadily progressing. The four prototype dataloggers are installed and have been proven reliable in the quarry operation. The data transmission works as planned. The raw data is processed by the AutoPLAN expert system. Based on that data a defined set of KPIs is and will be developed to enhance the quarry optimisation process from CSI. Further external sensors will be installed to enhance the validation process of the calculated KPIs.

List of Figures

Figure 1. Drone image of the treatment plant in the quarry Mammendorf.	6
Figure 2. Overview of the whole quarry Mammendorf with short site description.	7
Figure 3 Dump Truck (Caterpillar 775G) with installed data logger.....	9
Figure 4 Truck (Volvo FMX 500) with installed data logger.....	10
Figure 5 Excavator (Caterpillar 374) with installed data logger.	10
Figure 6 Wheel Loader (Komatsu WA 475) with installed data logger.....	11
Figure 7 Raw data tool for visualisation and data comparison and the number of available data sets.	12
Figure 8 Mapping tool including display of orthophotos and geofences.	12
Figure 9. Single KPI overview and calculation (here fuel consumption).....	13
Figure 10 Installation position of the belt scale 1.21 behind the pre-crusher.	14
Figure 11 Fixed fuel station (left) and mobile fuel station (upper right and chip reader (lower right).	15
Figure 12 The Sensor and Display of the installed tire-pressure-monitoring-system.	16
Figure 13 The external weight scale on a wheel loader.	16
Figure 14 Screenshot from the high-resolution point cloud used for developing the topographical model.....	17
Figure 15 Topographical Model of the quarry Mammendorf integrated in the AutoPLAN expert system.	17
Figure 16 Temporary Geofence structure for the quarry Mammendorf	18
Figure 17 List of files uploaded to the data lake from the quarry Mammendorf.....	19
Figure 18 Inlay of a sensor for the measurement of abnormalities of a crusher.	20
Figure 19 BIM Model.	20
Figure 20 Calculated Fuel use (l/h) for a given day.....	22
Figure 21 Calculated fuel use (l/h) for a given day in relation to the actual average use documented by the pilot.	22
Figure 22 Connection between the vehicle position and the 3D-geofences.....	23

List of Tables

Table 1 Defined machine KPIs for the pilot Mammendorf..... 21